

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D7.1 - DIAMOND Visual Identity and Website

WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate and Exploit

30/03/2023

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document among consortium partners to describe the development and design of the visual identity and other relevant specifications of the project, including the graphical charter for creating communication and dissemination material for all purposes. The deliverable also accompanies and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the DIAMOND project website.

It can also be used by policymakers and other stakeholder groups as a documentation of the visual identity of the DIAMOND project and as reference material for research projects that seek to explore options for efficient dissemination through a website, providing ideas of how information could be promoted and organised through a dedicated project website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The DIAMOND website will serve, according to the DoA, as a constant node aiming to present information on the project and disseminate its results, as well as act as a reference site with material and links related to the models produced and used, the themes analysed, other research projects and initiatives of relevance, and news on climate action and science. The development of the website is essential to the effective promotion of the project concept, progress, activities, results, and stakeholder engagement. The project's progress and outcomes will be published online. Furthermore, the visual identity of DIAMOND will convey the message of what the project is about and will communicate objectives, methods, and expected results to stakeholders.

This report provides a description of the website's design requirements and development process, its structure, as well as reference screenshots of its main sections. It also showcases how the website aims to serve as the hub of the DIAMOND project communication strategy by acting as a consolidated portal for all project-related information and by connecting to all publications and materials created in connection with the project. What is more, this report presents in detail the visual identity of the project.

The visual identity and the materials presented on the website will be updated as project needs to evolve.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report, and the project's website, which can be accessed at <http://www.climate-diamond.eu/>.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO CENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA'COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY SYSTEM OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITÄT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report accompanies and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the DIAMOND project visual identity and website.

Apart from the project logo, the DIAMOND visual identity encompasses a flyer to create visibility for partner countries in all languages of the consortium; a leaflet for dissemination to stakeholders, in all languages of the consortium; a poster for physical/online events organised by partners or relevant organisations as promotional material; a roll-up for policy events; and a presentation with basic information on the project, to be used as a template and regularly updated/adapted to audience/event.

The DIAMOND website can be found at the following address: <https://climate-diamond.eu/>. Designed based on the most recent practices and principles for web design, the DIAMOND website follows a modern, innovative, and user-friendly approach, presenting the project's concept and objectives in detail, containing the relevant material, and notably featuring one dedicated section for news and events and one for the project's key outputs: the six Integrated Assessment Models.

The purpose of this document is to describe the visual identity and website of the DIAMOND project, which is part of Task 7.1, "Creating the DIAMOND visual identity & website". Tools including information and communication means such as the logo, flyer, leaflet, poster, roll-up banner, and template project presentation are presented.

The project's website and visual identity will be constantly updated, allowing for engagement with the general public and for presenting project results, publications, news, events, and overall progress, expecting also the participation from partners as well as interactions with related projects and the broader scientific community, until the completion of the project.

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1 DIAMOND Visual Identity

1.1 The importance of a Visual Identity

It is important to create a simple but distinctive and appealing visual identity early on, one that would effectively convey what the project is about through applications such as the final logo and graphical charter; a flyer to create visibility for partner countries (in English and all languages of the consortium); leaflets for dissemination, featuring information on objectives, methods, and expected results (in English and all languages of the consortium); a poster for physical/online events organised by partners or relevant organisations as promotional material; a roll-up banner for policy events; and a presentation with basic information on the project, as a template to be regularly updated and appropriately adapted to any given audience/occasion.

The visual identity of a project consists of the colours, elements, and shapes used in the promotional materials and reports of the project. It conveys the scope and objectives of the project and aims to effectively unify the project outcomes.

1.2 Structure of the DIAMOND Visual Identity

The DIAMOND visual identity has been designed to support the concept of the project and includes elements and features that correspond to its topic. The shape used—i.e., the diamond—represents the project's relation with the six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs), which are represented in each side of the diamond, altogether comprising a diamond of models.

The logo colours have also been chosen carefully. Blue is the most universally appealing colour across the spectrum because of its non-polarising traits; it is used in corporate logos as it creates a sense of security while showing professionalism, and by various businesses related to software, finance, technology, etc. Yellow shows optimism and enlightenment but also caution; brands that seek to draw in consumers with a comforting, warm embrace, and youthful energy always look towards yellow.

The visual identity ensures a consistent, professional outreach towards the targeted audiences during the implementation of all Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities, via the production of harmonised project templates for use by partners in all internal and external project communication (presentations in conferences or policy/stakeholder events, reports and documents, publications, leaflets, etc.).

CMYK	84	39	15	0
RGB	18	131	177	
HEX	#1283b1			

CMYK	18	2	88	0
RGB	218	220	68	
HEX	#dad44			

CMYK	74	67	66	84
RGB	21	21	21	
HEX	#151515			

Figure 2. Logo/Colour Specifications

A b c

Black

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum

Bold

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Regular

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Title

Big Title

Font : Segoe UI
Styles : Black

H1

Heading 01

Font : Segoe UI
Styles : Black

H2

Heading 02

Font : Segoe UI
Styles : Black

Body Content

Donec ultrices cursus enim vel hendrerit. Vestibulum a nisl vel purus dictum laoreet. Donec tincidunt odio sed dolor consectetur interdum. Cras sit amet arcu libero. Maecenas dictum, sem ut pretium tincidunt, nisl velit ornare odio, porttitor fringilla lorem leo sed ante. Nunc nec faucibus sem. Nullam sed erat quam. Aliquam placerat dapibus justo, a euismod diam ultricies viverra.

Font : Segoe UI
Styles : Regular

Figure 3. Typeface

3 DIAMOND Project Flyer

The flyer contains a brief overview of DIAMOND with some fundamental information on the project, creating visibility about the project and all partners involved.

Project Flyer Size: A5

It includes:

- A brief description of the project scope and objectives
- The DIAMOND consortium member institutes’ logos.
- Contact Details

The DIAMOND Project Flyer will be distributed at conferences, meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific and policymaking communities. It was initially produced in English and will be available both electronically and in hard copy. In addition, it will be translated into all languages of the consortium. The digital version of the DIAMOND Flyer is available for download on the DIAMOND Website ([link](#)).

The DIAMOND Flyer is shown in Figure 4 and can also be found in ANNEX II in finer detail.

Figure 4. DIAMOND Project Flyer

4 DIAMOND Project Leaflet

A short DIAMOND Leaflet has been prepared for dissemination among academic researchers, policy-/decision-makers, European institutions, the civil society, and all other stakeholders, at conferences and/or other scientific meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific, industry, and policymaking communities and to all other interested parties. The promotional leaflet briefly describes the aim, objectives, approach, and consortium synthesis of the project. It is trifold and consists of six distinctive panels/sections, including one cover panel with a brief description, one panel on project objectives, two panels on project approach (work structure, with emphasis on expanding capabilities), one panel on partners' logos, and one panel on contact and social media details.

It was initially produced in English and will be available both electronically and in hard copy. Moreover, it will be translated into all partners' languages. The digital version of the DIAMOND Leaflet is available for download on the DIAMOND Website ([link](#)).

Project Leaflet Size: A4

The DIAMOND Leaflet is shown in Figure 5 and can also be found in ANNEX III in finer detail.

Figure 5. DIAMOND Project Leaflet

5 DIAMOND Project Poster

A publicity poster for DIAMOND has been created, to be used as promotional material at events organised by the partners or hosted by other relevant organisations or the European Commission (e.g., COP side-events, and regional Energy Modelling Platforms, such as the ECEMP, IAMC, openmod, etc.). The poster will be modified and updated as needed to convey new information in line with the project's progress. The digital version of the DIAMOND poster is available for download on the DIAMOND Website ([link](#)).

Project Poster Size: The Poster has been produced in two versions, in A3 and A0, to be used according to the needs of each event.

The poster includes:

- A quick glance at the DIAMOND concept and objectives
- Partners' Logos
- Contact Information
- Textual and graphic elements

The DIAMOND Project Poster is shown in Figure 6 and can also be found in ANNEX IV in finer detail.

Figure 6. DIAMOND Project Poster

6 DIAMOND Project Roll-up Banner

A DIAMOND roll-up banner has been created for future events organised by project partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. Both the logo and the core aim of the project are displayed on the top. All images, graphic and textual elements are clear and easy to read. The colours (yellow and blue) are in coherence with the project's visual identity. Social media channels are placed in the middle and all partners are presented towards the bottom.

Roll-up banner Size: 85 cm X 200 cm

The roll-up banner is portable and has its own retracting mechanism built from aluminium, which enables easy portability and setup. Aluminium banners are a popular eco-friendly option, primarily because of their ability to be easily recycled.

It includes:

- The logo and title of the project
- A brief description of the project's concept
- Partners' Logos
- Social media channels

The digital version of the DIAMOND roll-up banner is available for download on the DIAMOND Website ([link](#)).

The roll-up banner is shown in Figure 7 and can also be found in ANNEX V in finer detail.

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development

DIAMOND seeks to update, upgrade, and fully open six IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity.

It further enhances modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies.

The DIAMOND work structure includes the integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science.

It also includes developing a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and to co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establishing vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

Contact Details

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contact@climate-diamond.eu

Follow us on Instagram:
@climatediamond

Follow us on Twitter:
@climatediamond

Join us on LinkedIn:
@DIAMOND

www.climate-diamond.eu

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Figure 7. DIAMOND Project Roll-up

7 DIAMOND Project Presentation

A Project presentation has been created, containing basic information. More specifically, the presentation includes the DIAMOND consortium, objectives, methodological framework, IAM enhancements, model interlinkages, modelling ensemble, as well as contact information. It will be used by the partners as the main presentation tool, for dissemination purposes at relevant events. The infographic that has been included is custom-made representing various dimensions of the project process (modelling capacity, usability and stakeholder interactions, visualisation of results, etc.).

The standard presentation will be regularly updated, and it can be adapted by partners according to their specific needs (although the main project elements and EU funding will be displayed on all occasions).

The digital version of the DIAMOND Presentation is available for download on the DIAMOND Website ([link](#)).

The presentation template is shown in Figure 8 and can also be found in ANNEX VI in full detail.

Figure 8. DIAMOND Project Overview

8 DIAMOND Project Website

The DIAMOND website will serve, according to the DoA, as the central portal, aiming to present information on the project and disseminate its results, as well as acts as a reference site with material and links related to the models produced and used, the themes analysed, other research projects and initiatives of relevance, and news on climate action and science. The development of the website is essential to the effective promotion of the project concept, progress, activities, results, and stakeholder engagement. The project's progress and outcomes will be published online. The website includes straightforward, appealing messages for different stakeholder groups, enabling them to follow tailored project news.

The domain name of the project's website is <https://www.climate-diamond.eu>. It contains the name of the project, with the .eu extension denoting its European origin. The selected wording fulfils the primary requirements of a successful domain name: it is short, descriptive, and easy to remember.

The website is built in WordPress, which is a free, open-source content management system (CMS).

For measuring the website traffic and monitoring the visitors' behaviour, a connection with the Google Analytics service has been established and configured. The data insights coming from the DIAMOND website can be accessed directly from the Google Analytics interface.

8.1 Design

In terms of design, the website will be as accessible as possible, reflecting the inclusive approach of DIAMOND. The website's colour palette is carefully curated to be in line with the project logo and the general/overall visual identity. The DIAMOND website exhibits a clean and light interface, with contrasting colours for the text and background to make reading easier on the eye and with vibrant colours only used for emphasis (e.g., links) where necessary. Also, the project's website has innovative ideas depicted on the home page concerning the GIF as well as on the footer with the contrasting colours. The footer's colours, which are black and blue, have been selected to add a modern touch. What is more, clean and modern typography is utilised throughout the website, across all sections, with large fonts that are easier to read. On the technical implementation, the website is developed using responsive web design, enabling access from different screen sizes and devices.

Several design updates and improvements are anticipated in the upcoming months. The website's stock photos will be gradually updated and replaced with images that better portray DIAMOND; these images may have been taken during project-related events or may have been given by associated organisations. The purpose of these images is to illustrate many facets/dimensions of the project's scope and beyond, while highlighting our partners' practical applications. The WP7 team will always contact individuals appearing in images and get their consent before publishing them online.

Overall, the DIAMOND website is built following modern web design principles, and focusing on usability, accessibility, and intuitive navigation. To further improve search engine optimisation and place the website at the top of search engine results for relevant searches, a number of news items with pertinent keywords will be put/posted on a frequent basis.

Cookies are used on the website to enhance user surfing/browsing, and Google Analytics is used to produce aggregated, anonymised statistics of visitor activity. The Google Analytics statistics are being used by DIAMOND as a gauge for how well the project is being communicated through the website. DIAMOND employs IP anonymisation, which involves removing the final octet of the IP address before storing it, to prevent the collection of personally-identifying information. By utilising particular browser settings and add-ons, users may disable both cookies and Google Analytics tracking. Also, users of the website have the option to reject the use of cookies by

clicking on the appropriate pop-up on their initial visit. Detailed information about cookies and Google Analytics, their use, and the way to block them are provided in the privacy and cookies policy of the website. Last but not least, a WordPress Accessibility Plugin, a plugin that can help make the website accessible to users with disabilities, has already been installed.

A preview of the website's front page is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. DIAMOND Home Page

8.2 Structure and Content

The site can be navigated using the main menu links, which are located at the top part of every website page. This is a two-level navigation menu that aims to guide the visitor in a simple and intuitive manner. Currently, it contains the following items (Figure 10):

Figure 10. DIAMOND website structure (site map)

- The “Home” menu item scrolls the visitor to the home/landing page.
- The “About” menu item includes the title and the five sections, which contain all available information about the project’s concept, main objectives, work structure, members of the Consortium, and advisory board.
- The “News & Events” menu item contains links to all posts about news concerning the project, as well as events scheduled for DIAMOND that partners will attend or have already attended. It is the main place for those visitors that would like to stay in touch with the progress of DIAMOND.
- The “Open Science” menu item includes the title and a four-item submenu. The “Upgrading Models” section, where the six produced IAMs will be presented (in addition to their integration into the I2AM PARIS platform model documentation). The “Expanding Capabilities” section will contain other domains to be covered in DIAMOND (including circular economy; land sector and nature-based solutions; climate responses; finance, labour, and well-being; preferences, behavioural aspects and heterogeneity; and a finer detail of the electricity sector). The “Modelling Platform” section aims to promote transparency of our scientific capabilities and processes, assumptions, and results, providing background information and a direct link to the I2AM PARIS platform. The I2AM PARIS platform has been co-designed with stakeholders and enables modellers to communicate with one another and stakeholders to interact with modelling assumptions, scenarios, and results, in an informative and easy-to-digest way. The platform was delivered in the framework of the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project and is currently being enhanced within the Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT project. Finally, the “Synergies” section documents all activities (e.g., papers, briefs, events, etc.) jointly carried out with other relevant research projects and/or initiatives.
- The “Publications” menu item includes the title and four sections. These contain (a) Scientific Publications, one of the key means of disseminating the project’s results to the research/academic community and of providing scientific credibility for the project’s work; (b) Conferences, to present and discuss the project’s

results and facilitate interaction with collaborating communities; (c) Policy Briefs, showcasing significant policy recommendations from the action; and (d) Deliverables of the DIAMOND project, which will be consolidated and available in a series of branded reports. All the material in these sections will be available to download as well as shared on the most popular social media platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram).

- The “Communication” menu item includes the title and five sections: Newsletters and Press Releases (created with Mailerlite and incorporating inputs from all partners on progress and key outcomes of the project, as well as a GDPR-compliant subscription service); Videos (used for seminars/webinars/workshops covering the project’s broad modelling ensemble as well as disseminating DIAMOND results in a more effective way to appropriate audiences); Infographics (interactive or static infographics for better visualisation of the project’s results); Visual ID (presentation of all the visual identity of the project) and Media/Press (news coverage in non-scientific press). Materials in these sections can be shared on the most popular social media platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram).

8.3 Main elements of the Website pages

The DIAMOND pages consist of three basic design parts or blocks:

- the Header (at the top)
- the Footer (at the bottom)
- the Content (in between).

8.3.1 Header

The Header, as shown in Figure 11, contains the navigation menu and the search tool/bar, and remains constant for all website pages. It also remains visible on top even when the user scrolls down a page. The header also includes links to the project’s social media accounts (Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube).

Figure 11. DIAMOND website header

8.3.2 Footer

The Footer, as shown in the figure below, includes two sections of information. The left section contains a statement acknowledging funding by the European Union’s HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme, followed by a menu with Quick Links (currently: Concept, Consortium, and Contact page link) and the DIAMOND logo in white, which—when clicked—returns the visitor to the homepage. Also, on the left side there is a link to the Privacy & Cookies Policy. On the other hand, the right section contains the names and affiliations of the ICCS key contacts (Project Coordinator and Project Manager), as well as the social media accounts and a “Back to top” arrow. The Social Media accounts banner is displayed on every page of the website, just before the footer section. The colour black was selected to give a modern tone to the website and create contrast with the rest of the website, which is mainly blue.

Figure 12. DIAMOND website footer

The “Contact” page provides the visitor with the capacity to send an e-mail to the consortium, including an attachment of up to 2 MB. The name, email address, subject, and message are required, as is a CAPTCHA verification of the request and an agreement with the Privacy Policy. Once this information is provided and the message is sent, it is routed directly to the management team mailing list. What is more, there is a picture on the left side showing our appreciation for the message.

A sample of the “Contact” page is shown in the figure below.

Get in Touch

Have more questions? We'll help you find answers.

Your name

Your email

Subject

Your message

No file selected.

THANK
YOU.

We'll be in touch
shortly!

Figure 13. DIAMOND website “Contact” page

8.3.3 Home Page

The home page consists of nine sections, as shown in the sample in Figure 9, with the aim to attract the visitor's interest and briefly inform about the various aspects of the project.

1st section: Header

Please see Section 8.3.1 'Header'.

2nd section: Video

At first, the user will come across DIAMOND's modern full-screen looping kinetic typography video, which presents the concept and name of the project. There is an arrow that directs/guides the user to the rest of the content on the homepage.

3rd section: At a Glance

To highlight important numbers on the DIAMOND website in a way that captures the visitor's attention, an 'at a glance' bar showcases big, bold, animated "running numbers" as well as some static data, based on the project implementation. This currently captures the lifetime of the project, the numbers of Consortium partners, the six models upgraded, and the scenario exercises.

Figure 14. DIAMOND website "At a Glance" section

4th section: Publications

In this section, there are four context areas (the same that can be selected from the corresponding top menu items), dynamically displaying the number of scientific publications, conference participations, policy briefs & business guides, and media articles. Upon clicking on any of the four areas, the corresponding page is displayed.

Figure 15. DIAMOND website “Progress” section

5th section: News & Events

This section contains links to selected important events and other project-related news. By clicking on an item, the corresponding page is loaded and displayed. The “View more” button displays the “News & Events” page (the same page that is displayed when “News & Events” is selected from the corresponding top menu-item).

Our Latest News

Figure 16. DIAMOND website “News & Events” section

6th section: Models

This section contains a 3D diamond, each side of which presents one of the six IAMs of the project. Moving the mouse pointer over each of the sides, the name of the corresponding IAM and a short summary appear. At the bottom, there is a “Learn More” option to indicate that, when clicked, the corresponding page of the model item will be displayed.

Figure 17. DIAMOND website “Model” section

7th section: Partners

This section includes the 19 partners involved in the DIAMOND consortium. Each partner is represented by its abbreviated name. There are navigation arrows but there is also an auto-rotation mode. Each element tab can be chosen by the user.

Figure 18. DIAMOND website “Partners” section

8th section: Subscription banner (‘Subscribe to our Newsletter’)

Using a banner (Figure 19), users can input their email address and subscribe to the DIAMOND newsletter.

Figure 19. DIAMOND website “Newsletter & Social Media” section

9th section: Footer

Please see Section 8.3.2 ‘Footer’.

8.3.4 Other Pages

The rest of the pages, also called 'inside pages', can be categorised into "static content" pages and "dynamic content" pages. A static content page usually contains information that is not frequently altered (e.g., concept, objectives, work structure, project Consortium members, and advisory board). On the other hand, dynamic pages contain information that changes frequently, such as the News & Events, Publications, Communication, and Synergies sections.

An example of a static page is shown in Figure 20.

🔍 🌐 📄 🏠

- Home
- About
- News & Events
- Open Science
- Publications
- Communication
- Contact

Project Consortium

About

ICCS - Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
⌵

Country: Greece

The Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE) of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) was founded in 1992. The mission of ICCS is to support the deployment, the realisation and the growth of the research priorities of ECE mainly through seeking, pursuing and acquiring research funding via the competitive calls for research proposals that the European Commission had instigated.

The Decision Support Systems Lab / Energy Policy Unit (EPU-NTUA) operates within ICCS/NTUA and is a multidisciplinary scientific unit which provides academic training, carries out research and development projects, and offers management and decision support services across a wide range of complex business, socio-technical, and energy & climate policy/planning problems.

The E3MLab of ICCS/NTUA specializes in the construction and use of large-scale mathematical models covering the areas of Energy, the Economy and the Environment. Such models are used to make projections and analyse complex issues requiring system-wide consideration. Special emphasis is given to policy analysis and support.

<https://www.iccs.gr/en>

BC3 - Basque Centre for Climate Change
⌵

CESAR – Centre of Economic Scenario Analysis and Research
⌵

CICERO – CICERO Center for International Climate Research
⌵

CYI – The Cyprus Institute
⌵

E4SMA – Energy Engineering Economic Environment System Modelling and Analysis
⌵

HOLISTIC – HOLISTIC P.C.
⌵

COMILLAS - Comillas Pontifical University of Madrid
⌵

ISINNOVA - Institute of Studies for the Integration of Systems
⌵

SEURECO - Société Européenne d'Économie
⌵

UM - Maastricht University
⌵

ESMIA – Energy Super Modelers and International Analysts
⌵

UMD – University System of Maryland
⌵

EPFL - Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
⌵

ETH - Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zürich
⌵

UNIBAS – University of Basel
⌵

Imperial - Imperial College London
⌵

Oxford - University of Oxford
⌵

UCL – University College London
⌵

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Quick Links

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Project Coordinator: Prof. Haris Doukas | Energy Policy Unit, NTUA

Project Manager: Dr. Alexandros Nikas | Energy Policy Unit, NTUA

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Figure 20. DIAMOND website “Project Consortium” static page (preview)

An example of a dynamic page is shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. DIAMOND website “Scientific Publications” dynamic page

8.4 Special Features: Open Science: Upgrading Models – Expanding Capabilities

A comprehensive list of the project’s six flagship IAMs, covering the state of the art and their ambition, is presented

in the 'Upgrading Models' section. The models are lined up next to one another. To read the information on each IAM, one needs to click on it and a short text will pop up in different colours respecting the project's visual identity. It should be noted that this section features a simplified overview of the documentation of each model.

C

Figure 22. Brief overview of the six flagship IAMs of the DIAMOND project

Another list of significant sectors that go beyond the structural limitations of Integrated Assessment Modelling is showcased in the Expanding Capabilities section. The six responses are stacked vertically. To read the information on each one, the user must click on the title and a short text will pop up.

Figure 23. Brief overview of the models available in the “Expanding Capabilities” page

ANNEX I: DIAMOND Alternative Logos

Contact Details

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Visit us at:

www.climate-diamond.eu

ANNEX III: DIAMOND Project Leaflet

Who we are

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Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development

DIAMOND seeks to contribute to the development of the next generation of IAMs, for effective climate policy support; by the end of the project, six new or enhanced IAMs will be fully open and sufficiently equipped to scientifically underpin and support an accelerated transition towards circular, resilient, desirable, and sustainable climate neutrality.

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development.

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Objectives

"DIAMOND" aims to:

- » Produce iteratively updated, upgraded, open-source versions of six leading IAMs
- » Further enhance the capabilities of IAMs to assess the trade-offs and co-benefits of a transition to climate neutrality with other SDGs
- » Enable the systematic evaluation of interactions among climate change mitigation, adaptation, risks, physical impacts
- » Validate the capacity of the enhanced IAMs to support climate and other development policies and COVID19 recovery efforts at multi-level aspects
- » Transparently open all modelling enhancements to the wider modelling community
- » Develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions, legitimise the implementation process and model development, and optimise the communication of project results

Approach

CODESIGN

This component establishes, operationalises, and manages a co-creation mechanism that drives all model developments as well as scenario exercises in the project. This mechanism, actively placing actors from all relevant stakeholder groups (scientists, policymakers, industries, citizens) at the heart of the project, helps form mutual understanding toward co-producing and therefore co-owning models and knowledge

UPDATE & UPGRADE

Here, six IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes as well as in capacity development activities of leading international organisations are opened and advanced in terms of sectoral and technological detail, spatial and temporal resolution, and geographic granularity. Six IAM super-groups use the co-produced requirements and coordinate with one another toward upgrading—as well as updating and harmonising the parameters of producing GCAM-Europe, OMNIA, CLEWs-EU, GEMINI-E3 EU, NEMESIS-World, OPEN-PROM.

INTEGRATE & EXPAND

With a view to achieving a sustainable balance between model complexity on the one hand and usability/comprehension of results on the other, creating the next generation of IAM capabilities must go beyond advancements on the models themselves. This interdisciplinary block of activities creates linkages of the six enhanced IAMs with other models, tools, and theories from modelling science as well as social sciences and humanities, to expand the IAM feasibility space to enable to adequately address aspects of behaviour, finance, labour, equity, physical impacts, biodiversity, and broader sustainability within and around mitigation.

APPLY & EXPLORE

This block applies the co-produced model enhancements and linkages to explore questions driven by scientific and policy needs as well as engaged stakeholders. It first creates a scenario definition space that acknowledges the progress made in modelling science before understanding the outstanding research gaps. Based on this space, it explores mitigation in conjunction with broader sustainable development perspectives, as well as with physical impacts and adaptation, and carries out systematic assessments of disruptive events (pandemics, economic shocks, innovations, and weather events, etc.). It seeks to stretch the frontiers of climate-economy modelling science, by exploring mitigation vis-a-vis circularity performance, labour and finance dynamics, societal transformations, and alternative economic paradigms, and by providing a novel risk framing of the produced scenarios.

OPEN

This component establishes new business models for IAM transparency and openness as well as governs IAM development, integration, and application using these models. It includes diagnostics and evaluation protocols, development pipelines (versioning, open codes, software management), user-tailored libraries and data explorers in the IAM PARIS platform, and FAIR data management.

Notably, this block also creates and sustains communities of practice for all six IAMs, leveraging participation in relevant networks and consortia as well as already established communities underlying their development and use, thereby enhancing the openness, transparency, sustainability, usability, ownership, and relevance of the advanced IAMs and scenarios produced in the project.

Expanding Capabilities

Knowledge co-production envisaged in DIAMOND is a challenging task that must be carried out from a multi- (from different disciplines), inter- (across different disciplines), and trans-disciplinary lens (across actors and sectors). By developing appropriate methods and frameworks, scenarios will be developed and analysed, among others, for:

- » The circular economy
- » The land sector and nature-based solutions
- » Climate responses and fully integrated assessments
- » Preferences, behavioural aspects, and heterogeneity
- » A finer detail of the electricity sector

ANNEX IV: DIAMOND Project Poster

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development

DIAMOND seeks to update, upgrade, and fully open six IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity.

It further enhances modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies.

The DIAMOND work structure includes the integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science.

It also includes developing a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and to co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establishing vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

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ANNEX V: DIAMOND Project Roll-up Banner

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development

DIAMOND seeks to update, upgrade, and fully open six IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity.

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ANNEX VI: DIAMOND Project Fly Presentation

DIAMOND
www.climate-diamond.eu

Project Overview

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

ATHENS KICK-OFF MEETING (KOM) 8-9 SEPTEMBER 2022

Dr. Alexandros Nikas, Prof. Haris Doukas (NTUA)

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Overview

Title:	Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development (DIAMOND)
Funding:	European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (HE)
Lifetime:	December 2022 – November 2026 (48 months)
Coordination:	Energy Policy Unit, Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICSS)
Participants:	13 beneficiaries, 6 associated partners
Call/Grant:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-03/101081179

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Consortium

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Objectives

- O₁• Go beyond the state-of-the-art of six leading IAMs (increase detail, resolution & capacity)
- O₂• Enhance the capabilities of IAMs (SDGs interaction, political & behavioural aspects)
- O₃• Create robust, fully integrated assessment frameworks
- O₄• Expand the scenario space and uncertainty spectrum
- O₅• Open all modelling enhancements
- O₆• Develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions
- O₁• Go beyond the state-of-the-art of six leading IAMs (increase detail, resolution & capacity)
- O₂• Enhance the capabilities of IAMs (SDGs interaction, political & behavioural aspects)

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Methodology & Structure

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IAM enhancements

IAM Enhancements (WP3)	Integrated Assessment Models					
	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWs-EU	GEMINI-E3 EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
Open-source code						
Open datasets						
Improved regional disaggregation for Europe						
Improved regional disaggregation for the globe						
Improved temporal granularity and/or longer time horizon						
Increased sectoral detail						
Enhanced technological detail (including disruptive technologies)						
Improved emissions/pollutants coverage (e.g., SO ₂ , NO _x , PM ₁₀)						

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Model interlinkages

Model Interlinkages (WP4)	Integrated Assessment Models					
	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWs-EU	GEMINI-E3 EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
Circular economy modelling (LCA, MFA, ENGAGE)						
Land-use modelling (MAGPIE)						
Climate modelling (SILICONE, OpenSCM, Pattern Scaling)						
Labour & finance dynamics, operationalisation of well-being						
Behavioural aspects and preferences for climate action						
Household heterogeneity (CHANCE, FIDELIO)						
Electricity modelling (OpenTEPES)						

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Moving Science Forward

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Thank You

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